

Writ of the Three Sovereigns

also known as “Sanhuang wen”, “三皇文”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Japanese Religions, Chinese Religion, Text, Daoist text, Daoism, Divination

The Writ of the Three Sovereigns was originally a key source of local Southern Jiangnan lore in China during the early medieval period. Dated to around the third century, it collected esoteric techniques that can be traced back to the “masters of methods” (fangshi), regional ritual specialists and influential court advisors from third century BCE to the third century CE. The scripture was thought to have been revealed in Antiquity by high gods to the first three rulers of China, the legendary Three Sovereigns, in order to assist them in ordering the realm and attaining the powers that came with spiritual accomplishment. The bulk of the text is devoted to a series of potent talismans written in a celestial script that is indecipherable to common mortals. When deployed correctly, they can summon supernatural beings ranging from local deities to high-ranking gods so that practitioners can obtain their favor, their protection, or, more commonly, to inquire about future events. The practice has a visualization component since the divine beings manifest in the mind’s eye; accordingly, some scholars term it “visionary divination.” Other techniques that are associated with the scripture include a meditation method that involves generating a bodily god that is a perfect embryonic version of oneself (an enchymoma) and alchemical practices that consist of crafting medicines and elixirs. In the fifth and sixth centuries CE, the Writ of the Three Sovereigns became the centerpiece of one of the three core divisions of the nascent Daoist canon. As a result, it also became one of the foundational sources of early institutional Daoism. This propelled the text from the fairly self-contained context of local Jiangnan lore to a far broader empire-wide setting. The purported efficacy of its summoning techniques, through which, it was rumored, that deities could grant even the status of emperor or empress to practitioners, were quickly identified as potentially seditious by Tang imperial authorities. The scripture was summarily banned in 648 CE. All known copies were collected and destroyed in the capital. The text was replaced in the Daoist canon by the Scripture of the Way and Virtue (Daode jing). Nevertheless, some fragments survived in citations or manuscripts, enough that the Writ of the Three Sovereigns could be reconstructed, at least in part, by contemporary scholars. After the ban, during the Song dynasty (960–1279), the scripture was “rediscovered” as a result of renewed interest in its practices. A highly modified version, in actuality an antiquarian reconstruction, circulated around the tenth century, enjoying significant popularity among Daoists for a few centuries. Its tenets and methods spread throughout China once again. Later on, during the late medieval or early modern periods, the Writ of the Three Sovereigns reached as far as Japan.

Date Range: 200 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Early Medieval China

Region tags: China, Six Dynasties China, Early Medieval China

A rough extent of China during the early medieval period and into the early Tang dynasty

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Dominic Steavu, *The Writ of the Three Sovereigns: From Local Lore to Institutional Daoism*, Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 2019
- Source 2: Kristofer Schipper and Franciscus Verellen, eds., *The Taoist Canon, A Historical Companion to the Daozang*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2004; see relevant sections under 1.B.4 "Texts of the Dongshen Division," 260–268; 2.B.5 "Sanhuang Scriptures and Ritual," 501–508; and 3.B.2. "Sanhuang," 975–980
- Source 3: Yamada Takashi 山田俊, "Dōshinkyō no kisoteki kenkyū" 「洞神經」の基礎的研究 [Fundamental Study on the Corpus of the Cavern of Divinity]. Kumamoto: Kumamoto Prefectural University Press, 2010

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: N/A

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.kanripo.org/text/KR5c0021/000>
- Source 1 Description: Scripture of the Wondrous Essence of the Eight Emperors (Dongshen badi miaoqing jing 洞神八帝妙精經; DZ 640), sixth century; preserves the most substantial fragments of what was likely the original (3rd-4th century) Writ of the Three Sovereigns and its oral instructions
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.kanripo.org/text/KR5e0040/017>
- Source 2 Description: Chapter 25 of the Unsurpassed Secret Essentials (Wushang biyao 無上祕要; DZ 1138), ca. 580; preserves substantial fragments of what was likely the original (3rd-4th century) Writ of the Three Sovereigns and its oral instructions
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.kanripo.org/text/KR5g0011/000>
- Source 3 Description: Scripture of the Primordial Transformations of the Eight Emperors (Dongshen badi yuanbian jing 洞神八帝元變經; DZ 1202), seventh or eighth century; preserves some of fourth-century lore and practices that developed around the Writ of the Three Sovereigns and became synonymous with it in later periods

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Notes: The talismans that make up the core of the text were hand-written or carved into seals and impressed

 Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

– Specify: paper made of hemp, bamboo, mulberry, and other coarse fibers

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Unknown, but probably not

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: No

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Notes: In terms of personal/practitioner storage, the text would be kept at home in a secure place, probably on or close to an altar. It could be carried on one's person, usually tied at the waist, for apotropaic purposes. In terms of bibliographic storage, no original manuscripts survive. Various excerpts or passages from the text, including talismans, are preserved in the printed Zhengtong Daoist Canon of 1445. A transmission ritual associated with the text, which may or may not have been incorporated into later versions, survives in the form of Dunhuang manuscripts (S.6301, S.3750, BD11252, and P.2559).

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography or imagery present?

Select all that apply

– At home

↳ Are there distinct or notable features or attributes in the religious group's iconography or images?

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Deities have human appearances (usually, that of ministers, officials, or sovereigns), but their esoteric countenances are zoomorphic (chiefly reptilian, but also bovine, equine, and/or avian)

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Typically in judicial/administrative/imperial garb.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol)

– Yes

Notes: Deities are sometimes pictured in their "true shape" (zhenxing), which correspond to shadowy abstract patterns. In other instances, they are depicted by their "true names" (zhenming). These are curvilinear abstract symbols that resemble Chinese characters but are different from them. They are made up of a divine script that is illegible to common mortals.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Status objects (tools, weapons, mounts, throne, etc.)

– Yes

Notes: The text itself (and the talismans it contains) is a status object since it is bestowed only upon the most deserving of adepts.

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Judging from similar traditions, in some instances, portraits or depictions of important figures in the text's transmission lineage could have been used in ritual contexts.

↳ Supernatural narratives
– I don't know

↳ Human narratives
– I don't know

↳ Specify
–Specify: N/A

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– I don't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?
– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?
– Yes

Notes: The text spontaneously manifested itself to a deserving human recipient on a stone wall inside a cave on a famous peak. Mountain spirits deemed the recipient, who regularly meditated in the cave, worthy and in their capacity as emissaries of the high gods who produced the text, they revealed it to him. Formerly, in high antiquity, the text had been bestowed by Heaven/the Dao to the first three legendary sovereigns of China to help them pacify the land, create civilization, and install a human order over the realm

↳ Revealed by a high god?
– Yes

Notes: In high antiquity, the text was revealed by Heaven/the Dao to the first three legendary sovereigns of China to help them pacify the land, create civilization, and install a human order over the realm. Subsequently, local deities (i.e. mountain gods) would reveal it to only the most deserving of human adepts, typically one per

generation.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– Yes

↳ Inspired by high god?

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– Yes

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: Once the text was included in the early versions of the Daoist canon in the fifth century, the highest-ranking members of Daoist orthodoxy were entrusted with interpreting the scriptures. At the same time, since the text remained strongly connected to the local Southern/Jiangnan culture which spawned it a couple of centuries earlier, it also circulated through regional clan networks. For a while, those who obtained the text outside official/orthodox lineages could receive or even generate different interpretations of the text.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– No

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– No

Notes: The interpretations of local lineages have not survived so disagreements, if any, were not documented. By and large, the orthodox interpretation of the text is the one we are familiar with.

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– I don't know

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– No

Notes: In the context of institutional Daoist religion, yes: only high-ranking members of the clergy were permitted to transmit the scripture. In the context of local Southern/Jiangnan lore (or "vernacular religion"), no: in principle, any spiritually accomplished person could receive and transmit the scripture.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– Yes

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

Notes: The text manifested in celestial script, the written language that divine beings use to communicate between them. Common mortals are incapable of understanding it, but those who are exceptionally gifted or spiritually accomplished can decipher it. Celestial script appears to be similar to traditional Chinese seal script, but it is distinct and fundamentally different.

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– No

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– Yes

Notes: As far as the core talismans are concerned, they are written in divine celestial script.

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Prophet

– Divinity

– Institutions

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– No

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– Yes

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Notes: The audience is potentially unlimited, but the text was transmitted only to deserving initiates in the tradition.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: After the text and its tradition were disgraced and banned by government authorities (on account of its seditious potential) in the seventh century, they were rehabilitated in the late-eighth or ninth centuries and the reformed in the tenth.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– No

↳ Is it read?

– No

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: It is transmitted in the initiation rituals of institutional Daoism.

Notes: It is transmitted, as a ritual gage of achievement or rank, in the initiation rituals of institutional Daoism. Receiving the text marks induction into the most basic of the three highest levels of ordination in medieval Daoism. After a period of purification, adepts embark on a lengthy ritual composed of recitations, oaths, offerings, prostrations, visualizations, etc. The transmission/initiation rituals associated with the text have changed throughout the centuries, but a handful of documents from key historical periods in the development of Daoism provide snapshots of how they unfolded at different times.

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– I don't know

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Number of participants: 2

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: Variable

Notes: Originally, once per generation since only the most deserving of adepts were granted access to the text. With the institutionalization of Daoism and the text's inclusion in the Daoist canon, transmission/initiation rituals were conducted every time an adept reached the requisite level of seniority or achievement. These rituals were eventually performed for entire groups of adepts. In local communities, they could take place anywhere from once to several times per year, but at the scale of China writ large, they must have occurred very regularly.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– I don't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: There is some debate about the matter but ritual manuals that are closely associated with the transmission of the Writ of the Three Sovereigns mention cannabis-based incense and the consumption of cannabis flowers. Moreover, alcoholic libations are a common feature of Daoist rituals and ritual feasts. Finally, the fasting requirements, which include sleep and food deprivation, coupled with the rhythmic chanting and frenetic music of the ritual, could mimic the psychoactive or trance-inducing effects of certain intoxicants.

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– Yes

Notes: After periods of fasting which preceded the transmission/initiation rituals, usually, sizable feasts were woven into the rituals or closely followed them.

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it visible?

– Yes

↳ Is it hidden?

– No

↳ Can it be touched?

– Yes

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?

– Yes

Notes: Receiving it and holding it has ritual significance

↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?

– Yes

Notes: The text itself, as a physical object, is eminently powerful: having it in one's possession alone guarantees protection from physical injury, disease, natural disasters, or harm in general. However, in order to access its more advanced, esoteric functions--such as summoning deities to converse with them or have them do one's bidding--proper initiation is required. Once that initiation is complete (through rituals but also oral instruction), the esoteric functions of the text are unlocked; like the exoteric ones, they are embodied in the material text itself: with minor ritual preparations, simply wearing it on one's person can be sufficient to summon deities.

↳ Promotes knowledge?

– Yes

↳ Is the knowledge hidden?

– Yes

↳ Can it be unhidden or unlocked?

– Yes

↳ Is the knowledge occult?

– Yes

↳ Is the knowledge esoteric?

– Yes

↳ Other type of knowledge?

–Specify: There are different levels of esoteric knowledge to the scripture in principle requiring different levels of initiation

↳ Does the text serve a protective function?

– Yes

Notes: One of its principal functions is apotropaic.

↳ Does the text serve a healing function?

– Yes

↳ Physical healing

– Yes

↳ Mental/psychological healing

– Yes

Notes: Although not explicitly stated, mental/psychological was considered part and parcel of physical healing in classical Chinese medicine and in the scripture more specifically. Thus, by default, any physical healing included mental/psychological, and/or spiritual healing as well.

↳ Incubation

– I don't know

↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?

– No

↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?

– No

↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?

– No

↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: Its content is just as important as its materiality. As an ritual object and apotropaion, it has both adducive (summoning gods, good fortune, etc.) functions and expulsive (expelling demons, misfortune, etc.)

↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?

Please specify the substances in the sub-questions

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: It is accompanied, in its reconstructed version, by illustrations of talismans.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: It forms the central part of the Cavern of Divinity (Dongshen), one of the three earliest scriptural divisions of the Daoist canon.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: Through the text's inclusion in the Daoist canon and, more importantly, its use by religious representatives (chiefly priests) of the religion's orthodoxy

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

Notes: There were historical periods of canonical fluidity, but the most recent one dates

back to the mid 15th century. Different versions of the Daoist canon were compiled in the 19th and 20th centuries; these sometimes include older manuscripts that were excluded from the canon or newly-discovered local sources of importance, but by and large, the Cavern of Divinity (the sub-canon to which the Writ of the Three Sovereigns belongs) has not changed much since the mid 15th century.

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– No

Notes: Some debates or a re-evaluation of the text have infused the text with new life, especially in the Song (960-1279) dynasty--and to a lesser extent during the Ming (1368-1644), but in recent times, its position with respect to the Daoist canon has remained unchanged.

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– I don't know

Notes: It is explicitly scripture.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary? (Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Notes: The reconstructed text includes oral instructions, some of which were consisted of ritual instructions. In this capacity, certain sections of the text are essentially ritual manuals that explain how summoning or meditative practices for example, should be conducted. Moreover, a ritual manual that survives in a group of medieval Dunhuang manuscripts and was probably part of an early enlarged recension of the text describes in detail the transmission ritual for the Writ of the Three Sovereigns.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Other [specify]: Via supernatural forces, spiritual elect, student-teacher relationship and esoteric ritual, or kin relations, depending on the period and area under consideration

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: Belief in immortality is indicated in the text

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The Dao is equivalent to/is a supreme high-god.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Notes: In the text's tradition, Heaven is sometimes described as a manifestation of the Dao, but it is not equivalent to or above it. The Dao remains the ultimate principle, while Heaven is its ontologically lesser incarnation.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

Notes: Although the Dao also encompasses chthonic principles or realms.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

Notes: Not explicitly. But when it is manifested as Heaven, the emperor--who is not necessarily of noble birth or issued from an elite caste---is understood to be the "Son of Heaven." Ultimately, the Dao could be considered a kin relation to all living beings.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– No

Notes: Good and bad are relative, human, and therefore fallible concepts. The Dao is beyond good or bad.

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: Ubiquitous and omnipresent. It is all of creation but also precedes it and succeeds it.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– I don't know

Notes: the Dao is not a conscious entity. But its earthly manifestations, such as Lord Lao (the deified form of Laozi) do have knowledge of this world.

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

Notes: Only in the form of earthly incarnations. Otherwise, the Dao is above intervention and deliberate causal efficacy.

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– No

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
– Yes
Notes: Yes, since they are all ultimately manifestations of the supreme principle, the Dao.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
–Specify: n/a (see above)

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
– Yes

Notes: Indirectly, through lesser gods, divine beings, and manifestations, who can communicate on its behalf.

↳ In waking, everyday life
– No

↳ In dreams
– Yes

↳ In trance possession
– Yes

↳ Through divination practices
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists
– No

Notes: but also through religious specialists who channel intermediaries such as (lesser) gods or divine beings

↳ Only through monarch
– No

↳ Other form of communication with living
– Yes

Notes: In all cases, indirectly, through intermediaries, most often lesser gods, divine beings, and manifestations, who communicate on its behalf.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Yes

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– Yes

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– Yes

Notes: Certain (human) figures such as sages, immortals, or highly advanced adepts/masters, have a more direct access to the workings of the Dao, the supreme principle. In that instance, they can be described as having "inspired knowledge."

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– No

Notes: No, but years of dedicated practice, pure intention, and a certain predisposition to spiritual achievement (what is sometimes called having the "bones of immortals") are conducive to attaining inspired knowledge.

↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sight or vision beyond the five senses).

– Yes

Notes: All of the above (clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sight or vision beyond the five senses) but also a heightened understanding of this world, both sensorially and extra-sensorially.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: This depends on the interpretation of the term "gui" 鬼 which is sometimes translated as "demons" and other times translated as "ghosts" as in the manes or spirits of deceased humans.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: With the help of deities summoned by the text, the practitioner has access to the deity's knowledge (through questions). While lower-ranking deities have circumscribed or locally-specific knowledge, the highest ranking ones are omniscient. Moreover, in the text's tradition, sages and immortals, who are essentially highly-accomplished humans, can eventually access the same levels of knowledge as divine beings.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

Notes: They can, but this is exceedingly rare

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

Notes: They can, but this is not very common

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

Notes: Trance is, I would argue, an integral part of divination practice, so according to this text, deities are summoned when the practitioner is performing "visionary divination," i.e. is in trance.

↳ Through divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

Notes: Yes and no. If individual practitioners are initiated and sufficiently qualified, there is no need for an officiant; they can perform the ritual or undertake the practice themselves

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Through meditative practices

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: They can have indirect causal efficacy (especially with respect to negative outcomes, punishments, etc.), but when summoned, they have direct causal efficacy, typically a positive one.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

Notes: The lower-ranking deities can be mischievous or spiteful, but the higher ranking ones either exhibit neutral or positive emotions

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

Notes: The lower-ranking deities can be mischievous or spiteful, but the higher ranking ones either exhibit neutral or positive emotions

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

–Specify: Overall, these supernatural beings are emotionally neutral

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– No

Notes: Organized according to an administrative, i.e. bureaucratic model, with

sovereigns/emperors on top.

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

Notes: On the basis of bureaucratic/administrative/judicial principles

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Notes: In some instances, the power is locally circumscribed, in others, for higher-ranking beings, the power is universal

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: bureaucratic/administrative/judicial/imperial with some occasional kinship elements as well

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The titular "Three Sovereigns" that give their name to the scripture are understood to be human beings with divine origins or traits. They are either the offspring of humans and gods or are humans who have been divinized on account of completing a feat or displaying a character trait that has given them favor with the gods

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?

– Yes

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– No

Notes: Not in as much as they can be perceived by non-initiates. But human-divine beings can impact the fate and everyday life of humans without them realizing who the agents are.

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– Yes

Notes: Typically yes, through religious specialists or initiated adepts. However, punishments can be doled out indirectly by human-divine beings. In that case, they remain invisible but their impact is felt.

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: N/A

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text grants direct access to supernatural beings through its practices.

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, presuming they are properly initiated and spiritually-qualified

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural being/high god can remain hidden even to those in possession of the text if they are not properly initiated or qualified.

Are other categories of beings present?

– Incomprehensible?

Notes: there is an entire range of divine beings, from the lowly and common to the unfathomable, that can be summoned with the text (and are thereby mentioned in the text)

Does the text guide divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the extra (animal remains)

– No

↳ Divination through human communication?

– Yes

↳ Human being the vehicle for the oracle?

– Yes

↳ Human being the interpreter of the oracle?

– No

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified sex/gender?

– No

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified ethnicity?

– No

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified class?

– No

↳ Is sex-deprivation required?

– Yes

↳ Are intoxicants required?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, inasmuch as sleep and food deprivation along with trance-inducing chants and music are considered intoxicants. Incense is also specified for use and there is evidence that some incense was dipped in THC-rich cannabis oil. The incense was lit in meditation chambers that were roughly 10 ft. X 10 ft. and had very poor ventilation.

↳ Is physical ordeal required?

– Yes

Notes: A period of "purification" that involved isolation, sleep deprivation, and food deprivation among other requirements, lasting from three days to two weeks (sometimes up to three months), preceded the practice of "visionary divination"

↳ Divination through animal-behavior?

– No

Divination through non-living material?

– Smoke

Notes: Smoke divination is not specified in this text, but it is mentioned in other sources from more or less the same period. There is some speculation that practitioners could have "witnessed" deities manifesting and taking shape before their eyes in the thick plumes of incense smoke in their cramped meditation chambers.

Other form of divination:

– Specify: Divination through meditation ("visionary divination")

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: They can, but they do not necessarily or always do so. Some of the beings generate obstacles by nature and these can impact practitioners who do not approach them in a ritually correct manner.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: They can, but they do not necessarily or always do so. Some of the beings are generally benevolent and can reward practitioners who approach them in a ritually correct manner.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: There are precepts, some of which are moral in nature, others more concerned with ritual propriety, but in no case are morals or ethics emphasized

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)

– No

↳ Monogamy (females)

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

Notes: "Purification" period required for both males and females before embarking on practices or engaging in rituals

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– Yes

Notes: "Purification" period required for both males and females before embarking on practices or engaging in rituals

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: In the form of offerings only

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: Practices and rituals are drawn out over a number of days, weeks, or months

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: Purification rites, ritual offerings, and basic worship are required before embarking on the visualization/divination practices described in the scripture. They are also required when receiving or transmitting the text.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not specified. Small-scale rituals are purpose-specific.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Notes: Relatively complex rituals are undertaken when the text is transmitted. Later in its history, when the scripture was integrated in institutional Daoism (from around the fifth century), its transmission was used as part of larger more elaborate and often communal ordination ceremonies.

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Large-scale rituals for the purpose of initiation/transmission only. Size varies depending on size of community. Can range from 2-3 people to several hundred.

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes only. In other cases, the purification period, which involves fasting, sensory deprivation, and sleep deprivation, can simulate the effect of psychotropics or entheogens, especially when the ritual or practice involves long bouts of focused meditation

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– No

Notes: Originally, animal sacrifices were associated with the text, but after ritual reform, references were stricken from the surviving version of the text and/or citations thereof

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

- ↳ Are they mandatory?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?
 - No
- ↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?
 - Yes
 - Notes: In as much as aromatics ("incense") are used as offerings, but the olfactory dimension is not singled out.
- ↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')
 - Yes
- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: N/A
- ↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?
 - No
 - Notes: It is mandatory for the officiant/practitioner
- ↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?
 - No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A Spiritual Elect

Notes: Originally, the scripture was produced by the cultural/intellectual elite of Jiangnan on the basis

of the knowledge, traditions, and methods they inherited from the patrilineal forebears, the fangshi ("master of methods") ritual specialists of the Wu Kingdom and more remotely, of the Han dynasty. This Jiangnan cultural/intellectual elite also presented itself as a spiritual elite. In subsequent times, after its inclusion into institutional Daoism, later recensions or expansions of the scripture were produced by another group of spiritual electi, Daoist systematizers.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Spiritual Elect

Notes: In subsequent times, after its inclusion into institutional Daoism, later recensions or expansions of the scripture were produced by another group of spiritual electi, Daoist systematizers. Imperial authorities also promoted the scripture (after having banned it in the early part of the Tang dynasty).

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– An empire

Notes: Judging it potentially seditious on account of its power (reputed to "make emperors and empresses"), imperial authorities banned the text. They collected all known copies and destroyed them in 648. Only fragments have survived in the form of citations or descriptions, but these are sufficiently detailed to reconstruct an portrait of what the original scripture would have looked like, at least in part.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in the sense that a teacher/master not only transmits the text to the most deserving of disciples but also provides the crucial "oral instructions" for its use. Without these, the text remains inaccessible.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Notes: No, but a spiritual bureaucracy (which, ideally, informs the secular bureaucracy) is regulated by this text.

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: Some of the deities to which the practitioner has access via the text are military deities in charge of massive armies

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No